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**Transformation of e-commerce Strategies under the Influence of Innovative
Artificial Intelligence Solutions in the Digital Economy**

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Abstract. The purpose of the study is to analyze the impact of artificial intelligence on e-commerce management strategies and develop recommendations for their adaptation to modern digital challenges.

To achieve these objectives, the structural analysis of digital technologies, comparative study of business models, and evaluation of the effectiveness of artificial intelligence (hereinafter - AI) tools in interaction with consumers were used.

The study reveals how AI is changing approaches to the development of e-commerce in the context of digital transformation. It is determined that the use of AI technologies contributes to the improvement of business processes, personalization of interaction with consumers and increase in the effectiveness of marketing strategies. Special attention is paid to the issues of adaptation of companies to rapid market changes caused by the active development of digital technologies. It is noted that the introduction of AI allows companies to respond quickly to market changes,

increasing the accuracy of demand forecasting and optimizing pricing management. It is confirmed that the automation of customer interaction improves the level of service and contributes to strengthening customer loyalty.

The practical significance of the results obtained is to formulate recommendations for the use of AI in e-commerce, which relate to improving marketing strategies, increasing the level of analytics of consumer expectations, and improving data security.

The conclusions summarize that without a proper strategic approach, the use of AI can lead to excessive standardization of consumer experience, which will negatively affect the uniqueness of brands. The analysis made it possible to identify the main trends important for the formation of strategic decisions and patterns in the use of AI.

Promising areas for further research include analyzing the long-term impact of AI on brand management, assessing the level of consumer confidence in automated services, and developing new mechanisms for protecting information in the digital environment. Additionally, it is important to investigate how AI technologies can adapt to the cultural characteristics of consumers in different regions, which affects the global strategies of companies.

Keywords: digital commerce, business process automation, personalization of purchases, an adaptation of market strategies, forecasting consumer behaviour, data management.

Трансформація e-commerce стратегій під впливом інноваційних рішень штучного інтелекту в умовах цифрової економіки

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Анотація. Метою роботи є аналіз впливу штучного інтелекту на стратегії управління в електронній комерції та розроблення рекомендацій для їхньої адаптації до сучасних цифрових викликів.

Для досягнення поставлених завдань використано методи структурного аналізу цифрових технологій, порівняльного дослідження бізнес-моделей та оцінювання ефективності інструментів штучного інтелекту (далі – ШІ) у взаємодії зі споживачами.

У результатах дослідження з’ясовано, як ШІ змінює підходи до розвитку електронної комерції в умовах цифрової трансформації. Визначено, що використання ШІ-технологій сприяє вдосконаленню бізнес-процесів, персоналізації взаємодії зі споживачами та підвищенню ефективності маркетингових стратегій. Окрему увагу приділено питанням адаптації компаній до швидких змін ринку, що зумовлені активним розвитком цифрових технологій. Зазначено, що впровадження ШІ дозволяє компаніям швидко реагувати на зміни ринку, підвищуючи точність прогнозування попиту та оптимізуючи управління ціноутворенням. Підтверджено, що автоматизація взаємодії з клієнтами покращує рівень обслуговування та сприяє посиленню лояльності споживачів.

Практичне значення отриманих результатів полягає у формуванні рекомендацій щодо використання ШІ в електронній комерції, які стосуються вдосконалення маркетингових стратегій, підвищення рівня аналітики споживчих очікувань та покращення безпеки даних.

У висновках підсумовано, що без належного стратегічного підходу застосування ШІ може призвести до надмірної стандартизації споживчого досвіду, що негативно впливатиме на унікальність брендів. Здійснений аналіз дозволив виявити основні тенденції, важливі для формування стратегічних рішень, та закономірності в застосуванні ШІ.

Перспективними напрямками подальших досліджень є аналіз довготривалого впливу ШІ на управління брендом, оцінювання рівня довіри

споживачів до автоматизованих сервісів та розробка нових механізмів захисту інформації в цифровому середовищі. Додатково важливо дослідити, як ШІ-технології можуть адаптуватися до культурних особливостей споживачів у різних регіонах, що впливає на глобальні стратегії компаній.

Ключові слова: цифрова комерція, автоматизація бізнес-процесів, персоналізація покупок, адаптація ринкових стратегій, прогнозування споживчої поведінки, управління даними.

Problem statement. The modern development of e-commerce is heavily influenced by AI, which radically changes approaches to doing business in the digital economy. By implementing machine learning algorithms, data analytics, and predictive analytics, companies can better understand consumer needs, adapt marketing strategies, improve logistics, and make more accurate demand forecasts. Businesses that actively use these technologies respond faster to market changes, personalize customer interactions, and increase the efficiency of operational processes.

Expanding the digital space leads to an increase in information flows and, consequently, to higher requirements for the speed and accuracy of its processing. In this space, artificial intelligence plays an important role, allowing us to analyze large amounts of data, predict trends, and instantly adapt business strategies by changes in consumer behaviour.

In e-commerce, this means automating customer interaction processes and improving service quality, strengthening cybersecurity measures, and reducing fraud risks. Competition in the digital market forces companies to look for new approaches to integrating artificial intelligence into their business models. The efficiency of these processes determines their ability to adapt quickly, resist crisis changes, and achieve long-term success. The study of the impact of innovative AI solutions on e-commerce transformation is practically significant as it allows the identification of effective strategies that ensure stable business development in the digital economy.

Analysis of the latest research and publications. The development of e-commerce in the modern digital world is impossible without AI technologies that change traditional approaches to marketing, business management, demand generation, and financial performance assessment. Analyzing scientific developments in this area allows us to identify priority research areas.

One of the main areas is using AI tools in e-commerce marketing strategies. Researchers O. Kabanova, (О. Кабанова) I. Pashniak (О. Пашняк), and S. Vasylyk (С. Василик) [1] study the role of digital technologies in marketing campaigns, emphasizing the growing role of advertising personalization and automation of communications with customers. Researchers I. Sysoieva (І. Сисоєва) and O. Tsikhanovska (О. Ціхановська) [2] focus on global trends in digital marketing, considering algorithms for analyzing consumer behavioural patterns. At the same time, economist V. Serbin (В. Сербін) [3] explores the possibilities of using AI to promote goods and services, which allows companies to interact more effectively with the target audience and optimize advertising costs.

Another important aspect of the study is optimising business processes using AI technologies. Authors T. Muzychenko (Т. Музиченко), O. Skorba (О. Скорба), and A. Shevchuk (А. Шевчук) [4] study how automated AI systems help to ensure the efficiency of management processes and reduce costs. Researchers O. Lysak (О. Лисак), V. Tebenko (В. Тебенко), and L. Voltyanska (Л. Болтянська) [5] analyze innovative trade, warehouse accounting, and demand forecasting approaches, emphasising AI tools' capabilities in logistics. Scientists N. Rane, S. Choudhary, and J. Rane [6] focus on the problems and challenges that accompany the introduction of artificial intelligence into business management, as well as on finding ways to overcome them.

Besides, artificial intelligence plays a significant role in shaping consumer behaviour—the author of A. Svetailo (А. Светайло) [7] investigates how personalized AI solutions affect the efficiency of advertising budgets in B2C e-commerce, promoting better customer interaction. Researcher L. Khrais [8]

examines the impact of AI on consumer behaviour, emphasizing the importance of data analysis in predicting consumer decisions. The use of artificial intelligence to recognize consumer patterns, which allows businesses to offer relevant goods and services, is studied by S. Gochhait and co-authors [9].

The impact of AI marketing on sales and financial results of companies deserves special attention. Economists O. Marchenko (О. Марченко) and N. Shevchenko (Н. Шевченко) [10] analyze the effectiveness of SMM strategies based on artificial intelligence algorithms that help attract a wider audience. Researcher M. Madanchian [11] investigates how AI technologies affect sales through customer interaction automation, particularly with the help of chatbots and voice assistants. Bibliometric studies on the use of AI in e-commerce are summarized by B. Wamba et al. summarize [12]. The authors emphasize its importance for the long-term competitiveness of companies. Practical aspects of AI application in e-commerce with a focus on its potential to improve customer experience and business process management are considered by X. Song et al. [13].

AI technologies are radically changing e-commerce, opening up new opportunities for business development, improving marketing strategies, optimizing processes, and improving customer interaction.

Identification of previously unsolved parts of the overall problem. Despite the widespread use of AI tools in e-commerce, several important aspects require more in-depth attention. In particular, there is currently no universal approach to assessing the effectiveness of AI in different business models, which makes it difficult to adapt it for companies of different sizes. Also, there is insufficient research on how automation affects long-term brand interaction with customers, as excessive personalization can reduce emotional connection and consumer trust.

Forecasting demand based on previous information has limitations, as user behaviour changes rapidly due to new trends and external factors. An additional challenge is the lack of uniform regulatory standards and security measures, creating risks for businesses and consumers.

The proposed study will help to address the existing gaps in scientific knowledge by developing a systematic approach to assessing the real impact of artificial intelligence in e-commerce and identifying optimal strategies for its integration.

Formulation of the article's objectives (definition of tasks). The purpose of the article is to study changes in approaches to e-commerce based on artificial intelligence technologies in the digital economy.

In accordance with this goal, the following tasks are formulated:

1) to study the modern artificial intelligence technologies actively used in e-commerce, to assess their impact on business processes and to determine how automation and personalization of services change the interaction of companies with consumers;

2) to analyze the role of artificial intelligence in predicting changes in consumer expectations, managing reputational risks and transforming business models in response to digital challenges, as well as to identify the main challenges and risks arising from the use of AI, including aspects of cybersecurity and regulation;

3) to develop recommendations for the effective implementation of AI technologies in e-commerce business models, focusing on increasing their stability, competitiveness and adaptability to the dynamic conditions of the digital environment.

Summary of the main research material. Artificial intelligence is becoming an increasingly popular tool in e-commerce, helping businesses to better understand their customers, anticipate their needs, and automate key processes.

The overall growth of the global e-commerce market is not only a consequence of digitalization but also a result of strategic technological integration. One of the key drivers of this growth is the implementation of artificial intelligence tools that optimize logistics, automate marketing, and personalize user experiences. As illustrated in the chart below, global e-commerce sales have been steadily

increasing from 2021 to 2025, reaching 7.4 trillion USD in 2025. This growth correlates with the intensification of AI-based solutions in business processes, especially in predictive analytics and customer behavior modeling (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Global retail e-commerce sales 2021–2025

Source: compiled by the author on the basis of [14]

The data confirms the accelerated growth of the e-commerce sector, which reflects not only changing consumer preferences but also the effectiveness of AI-driven strategies. Companies that leverage artificial intelligence for automation and personalization have demonstrated higher scalability and responsiveness, which aligns with the global upward trend in digital commerce revenues.

Modern technologies allow companies to analyze huge amounts of information, quickly adapt to market changes, and offer customers a personalized experience. This improves the service level and allows businesses to operate more efficiently, reducing costs and increasing profitability. The impact of modern AI technologies on the development of business models in e-commerce is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Impact of modern AI technologies on the development of business models in
e-commerce

AI technology	How it works	What it changes in e-commerce
Machine learning	Analyzes customer behavior, predicts trends, and generates personalized recommendations	Helps companies to better identify customer needs and improve customer experience
Computer vision	Recognizes images, analyzes products, and supports virtual try-on	Improves online product interaction and reduces the number of returns
Neural networks	Identifies patterns in large data sets, helps automate processes	Enables more efficient inventory management and demand forecasting
Natural language processing (NLP)	Analyzes text queries, answers customer questions via chatbots	Makes service faster and more affordable
Analytical systems	Track the effectiveness of marketing campaigns, evaluate the behavior of competitors	Allows you to quickly adjust business strategies

Source: compiled by the author on the basis of [1; 8; 9, p. 1603; 15]

In real life, all these technologies are already changing how companies do business. For example, machine learning algorithms allow marketers to better understand customer interests, helping to create more relevant offers and promotions. Thanks to computer vision, customers can view products in 3D, try them on in a virtual space, and make more informed decisions, which is especially important for the fashion and electronics industries.

Neural networks are used to automatically analyze demand, which helps companies avoid shortages or overstocking. Chatbots based on natural language processing can answer customer questions in real-time, reducing the workload of support operators.

Dynamic pricing allows businesses to respond flexibly to changing market conditions by automatically adjusting prices to stay competitive.

Modern AI technologies open up new opportunities for e-commerce. Companies that actively implement them can adapt more quickly to changes in consumer behaviour, increase the efficiency of their activities and create a unique experience for each client [9, p. 1602]. As a result, businesses become not only more profitable but also more focused on the needs of their users, which is an important factor for success in the digital economy. Automation and personalization have become the main directions of modern business development, allowing companies to better understand their customers and respond to their needs faster. The use of artificial intelligence technologies helps not only to analyze consumer behaviour but also to predict future requests, which allows businesses to offer the right solutions in a timely manner. Thanks to intelligent algorithms, companies can improve service, increase the effectiveness of advertising campaigns, and build strong long-term relationships with customers (Table 2).

Table 2

Key areas of changes in business interaction with customers under the influence of artificial intelligence

Direction of changes	Features	Example of impact
Predictive maintenance	Analyzes customer actions and predicts their needs even before they contact you	A bank can automatically offer an increase in the credit limit if the system detects that the user has a suitable financial profile
Personalization of recommendations	Takes into account customer interests in real time, offering products that best match their preferences	Online stores update product selections based on recent purchases and browsing, boosting sales
Emotional analytics	Recognizes the user's mood through text messages or audio analysis	Chatbot changes the style of communication, adapting to the emotional state of the customer, which makes communication more comfortable
Automatic analysis of complaints	Identifies negative trends in customer reviews and messages	Businesses are able to respond quickly to problems and fix them before massive consumer dissatisfaction
Flexible loyalty programs	Offers personalized bonuses and discounts according to consumption style	Airlines analyze the frequency of customer flights and offer individual discounts or bonuses

Source: compiled by the author on the basis of [1; 2, p. 277; 7; 8; 11; 15]

Real examples of the application of these technologies demonstrate their effectiveness in various business areas. The Starbucks company actively uses artificial intelligence in its mobile application to improve the customer experience. The Digital Flywheel system analyzes user preferences, order history, and even weather conditions to offer the most appropriate drink or dish [16]. For example, if a customer usually buys coffee in the morning, the app can offer them a special offer at that time or recommend a new drink that matches their taste preferences. In addition, if the customer is near a Starbucks coffee shop, the system can send a reminder, increasing the likelihood of a purchase.

Amazon uses advanced personalization by analyzing the browsing and purchase history of each customer [17]. Its algorithms recommend products that best suit the buyer's interests. For example, if a user orders a smartphone, the system can offer them accessories for this model [4]. Additionally, Amazon uses predictive

analytics to optimize logistics - goods can be sent to warehouses near the location of potential buyers even before the order is placed, which significantly reduces delivery time.

Advertising platforms Facebook Ads [18] and Google Ads [19] are also actively using AI to improve the efficiency of marketing campaigns. Their algorithms analyze user behavior to identify the most interested audience [17]. For example, if a user regularly browses content about sportswear, the system will automatically show them similar ads, which increases the likelihood of a purchase. This allows companies to spend their advertising budget more rationally, attracting those customers who are actually interested in the products.

Wowcher has implemented AI to automate its social media content strategy [20]. Algorithms study subscriber reactions and analyze which content is most attractive to different audience segments. This allows Wowcher to post offers that best meet the interests of consumers, thereby increasing engagement and sales. The introduction of artificial intelligence into service automation and personalization of customer interaction allows businesses to work more efficiently by offering users the services and products they really need. This contributes to the growth of brand trust, increased sales, and strengthened competitive position of companies in the dynamic digital environment.

Artificial intelligence is fundamentally changing the way companies manage their business in the digital age. Businesses can no longer adhere to rigidly fixed business models, as they now need flexibility, speed of adaptation, and the ability to anticipate future changes. AI helps to build effective strategies that take into account consumer interests, market fluctuations, and reputational risks, allowing companies not only to respond to challenges but also to actively shape trends.

Strategic approaches that have remained unchanged for decades are undergoing a transformation. Standard marketing campaigns are giving way to personalized strategies that take into account the behavior of each client [3, p. 89]. Reputation management has become proactive: companies do not just respond to

negative feedback but predict risks and eliminate them at the stage of public opinion formation. Financial models have also changed: universal pricing policies are no longer effective, as AI allows companies to flexibly adjust prices to meet demand and market expectations (Table 3).

Table 3

Transformation of e-commerce strategies depending on the type of
enterprise

Type of enterprise	Traditional strategy	How the strategy has changed after the introduction of AI	Strategic implications for business
Mass retail (supermarkets, retail chains)	Fixed prices, same marketing campaigns for everyone	Flexible pricing, automatic management of promotional campaigns	Increased responsiveness to changes in demand, reduced costs
Premium segment (branded goods, luxury goods)	Standard discounts, limited customer interaction	Personalized offers, flexible loyalty systems	Strengthening communication with customers, increasing retention
Media and digital services (streaming platforms, educational services)	Same rates for all, static content	Dynamic content updates, adaptive subscription models	Revenue optimization, increased user engagement
Logistics and delivery (online retail, marketplaces)	Fixed routes, standard delivery times	AI-optimized logistics, variable delivery options	Reduced costs, increased customer satisfaction
Financial services (online banking, fintech companies)	Unified banking offers, static credit terms	Dynamic lending, personalized financial products	Increase profitability, strengthen customer trust

Source: author's own development

Strategic changes have their characteristics in each sector. In the mass retail sector, companies gradually abandon rigidly fixed promotions and move to dynamic pricing. For example, Zara uses AI to analyze local sales, which allows it to quickly change store assortment, optimize inventory and reduce costs [21].

The premium segment pays more attention to building long-term relationships with customers. Nike, for example, has changed its strategy of interaction with customers by using AI to create customized offers in its app, which contributes not only to sales but also to loyalty [22].

AI allows platforms to adapt their services to audience preferences faster in the media sector. The American media service provider Netflix uses AI to make personalized recommendations and analyze consumer behaviour, which allows it to

create unique offers for different user segments and test adaptive subscription models [23].

Logistics companies are changing their strategies to focus on speed and flexibility [9, p. 1604]. Using AI to predict routes and analyze delivery times can reduce costs and improve order fulfillment accuracy.

Financial services are also adapting to the new environment. Banks are increasingly implementing AI analytics to create personalized loan offers for customers, adjusting the terms to their financial habits. This allows not only increased bank profits but also increased trust in the financial institution.

Thus, AI is changing both individual processes and business models, forcing companies to reconsider their strategic approaches. In the digital era, adaptability, speed of decision-making, and the ability to work with large amounts of information have become important success factors. However, the use of AI technologies is accompanied by risks related to data security, legal regulation, and socioeconomic changes.

One of the main problems is the threat of cyberattacks. AI systems work with huge amounts of data, which makes them vulnerable to manipulation [4]. Insufficient protection can lead to algorithmic distortion, which is especially dangerous in the financial sector, medicine, and critical infrastructures. Additionally, there is a risk of information leakage, which threatens the confidentiality of user data [6, p. 26]. Legal regulation also does not keep pace with the rapid development of technology. The absence of uniform standards across countries creates legal conflicts, in particular regarding liability for decisions made by AI. This is especially true for automated systems that affect credit decisions, medical diagnostics, or the justice system. The lack of transparency of algorithms remains another challenge, as the complexity of their work often makes it impossible to explain the decisions made, which can cause distrust among users.

Automation of business processes leads to a reduction in the number of jobs. Manufacturing, logistics, and the financial sector are actively implementing AI,

which changes employee requirements and requires expanded retraining programs [5, p. 162]. At the same time, companies are forced to adapt their HR strategies to balance technological progress with social responsibility.

An additional risk is associated with the use of AI in the field of information security [4]. Modern algorithms can generate fake news, create disinformation campaigns, and influence public opinion. This jeopardizes the credibility of information, making it difficult to verify and confirm.

Effective implementation of artificial intelligence in e-commerce requires flexible strategies that will help businesses adapt to digital changes and remain competitive. The use of AI should be based on the analysis of consumer expectations, which allows for forecasting demand and promptly changing approaches to sales and marketing. Automated analysis of large volumes of data helps to react to changes and get ahead of them, forming personalized offers even before the customer shows interest.

For effective reputation management, it is worth integrating AI into the public opinion monitoring system, which allows you to quickly identify potential reputational threats and prevent negative scenarios before they develop. Timely analysis of consumer feedback and social media helps companies resolve crisis situations and build a positive image by adapting communication to the audience's expectations.

The flexibility of the business model is enhanced by AI-optimized pricing and personalized services. Dynamic price regulation that considers consumer behavioural patterns and market conditions allows for an increase in customer loyalty and maximizes profits. AI in logistics improves warehouse inventory management and increases supply chain efficiency, which is critical for business stability.

To fully realize the potential of AI, companies need to adapt their internal processes, ensuring data security, staff training, and modernization of management systems. An integrated approach to technology implementation allows the

optimization of business operations and the creation of a more sustainable and adaptive e-commerce ecosystem capable of responding effectively to market challenges.

Conclusions. This analysis suggests that the introduction of artificial intelligence has a significant impact on the development of e-commerce, contributing to a deeper understanding of consumer needs, increasing the efficiency of business processes and faster adaptation to market changes. By using AI technologies, companies can personalise customer interactions and predict their needs, optimizing their assortment, pricing, and marketing strategies.

As opportunities grow, so do the number of challenges. Businesses face data security issues, the need for accurate information analysis, and rapid changes in regulatory requirements. Dependence on the quality of input data and the risks of cyberattacks requires thoughtful approaches to information security. Integrating AI into business models requires a strategic approach that involves the gradual adaptation of technologies at all levels of management.

To use AI effectively, businesses should focus on implementing consumer demand forecasting tools, improving reputation management through public opinion analysis, and applying dynamic algorithms to adjust prices and logistics. Additional attention should be paid to security issues, as consumer trust is essential for success in the digital environment.

Further research may include exploring the potential of AI in long-term planning, analyzing the effectiveness of different marketing process automation approaches, and assessing new algorithms' impact on the stability of e-commerce business models.

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